

CHOOSING THE RIGHT CAREER IS A DIFFICULT AND CHALLENGING TASK

N.M.Qayumova

a teacher, Bukhara State University

S.N.Nizomiddinova

a student, Bukhara State University

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Annotation: This article analyzes the challenges of choosing the right career and how to find solutions to them. The career planning process are also mentioned in the article.

Key words: career, work, job, to select, society, choice, education, goal, opportunity, decision.

Traditionally, the term "career" was related with paid work and referred to a particular vocation. The concept of a career is now understood to be a continual process of learning and growth. Training, education, employment, work experience, community activities, enterprise activities, employment, diverse life roles, volunteer work, and leisure activities are all examples of activities that support a career.

For many of school leavers, finishing high school marks the start of their independent lives. They have a variety of options, including technical schools, institutions, and universities. But selecting a career from among the more than 2000 that already exist in the globe is not an easy task. There were just a few jobs available centuries ago: farmers, bakers, butchers, or salespeople. There are thousands of different job types available today, and more are continually being created. And because it affects our future selves in a variety of ways, selecting a job has always been a crucial and challenging issue. It is among the most significant choices that someone will ever make. A person spends over half of their lives at work. Making the appropriate profession choice is very crucial. According to psychologists, a person's future career should be chosen based on their skills and qualities. To make the best decision, you must assess your skills, interests, and goals as well as your interests and talents.

One of the most significant decisions you will ever make is what sort of job to pursue. You will need to give this decision a lot of thought before you decide who you are, what you enjoy doing, and what you are good at. Choosing a future job while in school has certain benefits. It provides a target to work toward and makes it possible to select an appropriate, suitable course of study. You must be realistic about your interests and skills while making decisions regarding your future. On the one hand, the modern world offers a wide variety of potential

career paths thanks to its numerous professions and employment. A young person can pursue careers in business and industry, farming, research and education, medical, services, the arts, and media, to name just a few. On the other hand, a poor career decision is a truly awful error in today's society with its crises, unemployment, and inflation. Even if you pick a vocation you absolutely enjoy, finding work might be challenging. Alternately, you may pick a job you like that pays little. In addition, a young person's parents typically have their own preferences for professional paths. Some parents are more democratic and let the youngster to make his own decisions about his destiny. Some try to push the youngster to choose one job over another and are repressive and overprotective. In this situation, they frequently make an effort to make up for their own unfulfilled aspirations and opportunities squandered. When parents see their child has talent in a certain area, they may try to influence him to pursue that career path whether he like it or not. . To make it easier for the young people, there is some professional advice. The young guy should begin this procedure as soon as possible, preferably in the tenth form. You should decide if you want to pursue higher education or pursue a trade and a job search. The choice is the individual's, however keep in mind that pursuing further education will provide you more opportunities and qualify you for skilled employment. You should decide what you want to major in or what you want to study in college. To assist with this phase, you might want to attempt any of these career evaluation exams. Additionally, you will undoubtedly receive advice from your relatives, friends, high school instructors, and guidance counsellors. The demand for a certain career on the job market is another thing to take into account.

Your problems may grow significantly if you choose a vocation where there are little job prospects.

Planning your career is a continuous activity that may assist you in controlling your learning and growth. Career planning is the ongoing process of considering your interests, values, skills, and preferences; investigating the life, work, and educational options that are open to you; ensuring that your work is compatible with your personal circumstances; and continuously adjusting your work and learning plans to help you manage the changes in your life and the workplace. There are four steps in the career planning process:

Understanding oneself is the first step: The following questions should be addressed in this step:

What do I hope to achieve in my career or job?

What do I enjoy doing?

What do I do well?

What matters most to me?

The second phase is known as learning. At this step, you should research the careers and academic fields that appeal to you. At this level, you should research careers that interest you and consider how your interests and talents align with each one.

The next stage is making decisions. This stage involves comparing your options, narrowing down your choices and thinking about what suits you best at this point in time.

The final step is taking action. The measures you must take to implement your strategy should be planned in the last stage.

In conclusion, choose a career is a difficult process. Finding the ideal fit between your personality, interests, and talents is key. Your chosen profession or line of work requires the appropriate training and work experience. Not all jobs require a degree, and those that do are in high demand right now and meet societal demands. Learning is the greatest adventure of all, and having a high level of education gives you the upper hand, a standing in society, and most importantly, self-satisfaction. And now that graduation is not far off, a career sounds appealing if you have a higher education, good working conditions, a stable salary, a job that fits your interests, is not monotonous, will lead to promotion in the future, will help you establish yourself in life, will allow you to be independent, will give you the chance to develop special skills, and, of course, if you are able to pursue it and can channel your interests into it.

References:

1. Paul Phifer. College majors and careers: A resource guide for effective life planning. New York. Ferguson. 2009.
2. Kerry Hannon. What's next? Follow your passion and find your dream job. Chronicle books. 216 pages.
3. www.professions.com